

Functional molecular gels – a brief review[†]

Ramesh Kandaneli, Sandip Bhowmik and Uday Maitra*

Department of Organic Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-560 012, India

E-mail : maitra@orgchem.iisc.ernet.in Fax : +91-80 2360 0529

Manuscript received 08 November 2011, accepted 09 November 2011

Introduction

The organization of small molecules into larger ordered structures has been one of the most intriguing features of life, be it the formation of a tobacco mosaic virus or a functional living cell. Nature has amply demonstrated the significance of these molecular arrangements in all types of life forms. The fact that the function of these assemblies depends heavily on their three dimensional arrangements and not only on the individual molecular structures is a clear manifestation of the profound importance of the supramolecular interactions¹. Naturally, over the past few decades the study of supramolecular assemblies of small organic molecules has grown into an important field of research. The detailed study of the nature of these interactions has not only provided useful insights into the structure-function relationship but has also provided us with tools to create novel systems that can have potential applications². In this regard, one of the most interesting architectures that has gained prominence in the past few decades are the **supramolecular gels**. A gel can be easily identified by a simple inversion test and are generally formed due to the immobilization of solvent molecules in a three dimensional entangled network³. The definition that is most generally accepted is the one advanced by Flory in 1974 that “a gel has a continuous structure that is permanent on the analytical time scale and is solidlike in its rheological behavior”. In case of polymeric gels, the long chain polymers provide the three dimensional matrix for immobilization whereas for small organic gelators the supramolecular interactions govern their assembly and eventual formation of the SAFINs. These polymer gels are often found to have superior material properties while the supramolecular gels enjoy several advantages of their own. The most important feature is the dynamic nature of the assemblies arising from the reversible non-covalent interactions like H-bonding,

π - π stacking, metal-coordination, van der Waals forces etc.⁴. The nature of interactions present in these systems makes it possible to modulate the physical properties by applying external stimuli, depending upon which a great number of functional materials can be designed.

The nature of the stimuli can vary from photons, cations, anions, redox modulators to acids or bases. Parameters such as temperature or solvent change can also bring significant changes in the properties of the self-assembled systems. These responsive supramolecular assemblies thus can act as a potential indicator system for changes in the immediate environment. The response generated can often be recorded by spectroscopic techniques or by other physical measurements.

Owing to these wonderful possibilities study of these assemblies have generated widespread interest in chemistry, biology, materials etc. A few examples of supramolecular gels which are responsive to various external stimuli are discussed in this brief review.

Stimuli responsive systems

pH responsive systems

A highly fluorescent pH responsive system was reported by Young's group. This system contains a chromophore which helps in aggregation and finally exhibits Aggregation-Induced Enhanced Emission (AIEE)⁵. Compound **1** formed a gel in *n*-butanol with high fluorescence emission in its gel state and almost 170 times more than that in the sol state (Fig. 1). Protonation of the pyridine

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Fig. 1. (a) Gel and sol states of **1** in *n*-butanol. The photograph in the inset shows the sol and gel of **1** (under UV 365 nm). (b) Photoluminescence (PL) spectra of **1** in gel and sol state. The enhancement in fluorescence intensity calculated from the integral areas of PL spectra. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 5. (© 2008 American Chemical Society).

Fig. 2. (a) and (b) SEM images of xerogels of **2**. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 6. (© 2001 American Chemical Society).

nitrogen of **1** in its gel state leads from Gel to Sol transition and concomitant decrease in the fluorescence in reversible manner retaining high fluorescence emission in the gel state.

More typical examples of pH responsive supramolecular assemblies include host-guest type of systems. Crown ethers, widely considered as the first generation of supramolecular hosts, have served for long as a typical design template for the construction of many functional host-guest assemblies. Besides pH, the self-aggregation can also be modulated by added metal ions.

Exploring these systems further, Shinkai *et al.* have reported a crown-appended cholesterol-based organogelator (**2**) with two cholesterol skeletons as a chiral aggregate-forming motif⁶. This molecule was found to gel a wide range of polar protic and aprotic organic solvents. Though the major interaction is the host-guest type between the quaternary amine and the crown ether moiety, the appended cholesterol moieties also play a pivotal role in the assembly. The gels also showed interesting helical morphology in the SEM [Fig. 2(a) and (b)] and TEM which were shown to be easily transcribed to TEOS par-

ticles to obtain helical silica nanoribbons. When the origin of chirality was investigated in details, the macroscopic helicity was found to be exactly opposite to the microscopic chirality established by **2** in its CD spectrum.

Huang *et al.* reported the design and synthesis of a novel dual responsive supramolecular polymer gel, which is constructed from a heteroditopic A-B monomer **3** utilizing the reversible host-guest interactions between dibenzo[24]crown-8 and its complementary guest dibenzylammonium salt (DBA)⁷. The formation of supramolecular polymers is envisioned to be a result of these interactions. The complexation behavior of the monomer was further established by NMR studies which clearly showed the aggregation pattern. Furthermore, the authors have demonstrated that the gels also serve as po-

tential pH controlled (Fig. 3) release vehicles for drugs as they have shown effective transport and release of a model compound Rhodamine B.

Cation responsive systems

Along with pH sensitivity another desirable attribute for the design of responsive supramolecular assemblies is a response to added cations and anions. Recently Schneider *et al.* have found a supramolecular assembly that was shown to be responsive towards a metal ion⁸. They have demonstrated Zn²⁺ triggered hydrogelation by a 20 residue β -hairpin peptide **4**. To achieve the desired response, an unnatural metal binding amino acid 3-amidoethoxy-aminodiacetoxy-2-aminopropionic acid was incorporated onto the peptide which is responsible for the metal responsive gelation process. The binding of metal to this site

Fig. 3. Showing the reversible responsive nature of **3** gel to dilution, thermal changes and to pH. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 8. (© 2011 Wiley VCH).

Fig. 4. (a) Oscillatory rheological dynamic time sweep of 0.5 wt% ZnBHP in pH 7.4 buffer (50 mM BTP) with 50 mM NaCl at 30°C. G' (●) and G'' (□) are the storage modulus and loss modulus, respectively. (b) 0.5 wt% ZnBHP bulk samples in pH 7.4 buffer (50 mM BTP) with 50 mM NaCl at 30°C in the presence and absence of 1.0 equivalent of ZnCl₂. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 8. (© 2011 Wiley VCH).

causes the side chain of this residue to become neutral thus significantly lowering the energy barrier needed for folding of the peptide which can then self-assemble to form beta sheet enriched fibrils (Fig. 4).

Another interesting example shows Ag^+ as the metal ion responsible for inducing gelation⁹. Ag^+ is often a preferred metal ion to design responsive gels because of its ready reactivity towards halide ions to form insoluble silver halides. These gels are often found to be chemo reversible in nature and the sol-gel transitions can be caused rather easily by switching between added Ag^+ and the halide ions. The strategy has been extensively used to obtain halide responsive gels. Compound **5** represents one of such examples where Ag^+ coordinates with the pyridine moieties which in turn results in the process of self assembly resulting in a hydrogel. Upon the addition of halide ions like Cl^- , Br^- , I^- the gel breaks down resulting in the formation of a sol.

Anion responsive systems

Along similar lines Steed *et al.* have reported an anion responsive gel system based on the well known class of bis-urea derivatives as the LMWG¹⁰. They prepared several homologous gelator molecules with varying chain lengths. These gels were shown to be sensitive towards certain anions (Cl^- , NO_3^- , BF_4^- etc.) and broke upon their addition to the gel. More remarkably, they also observed that switching the spacer length of a bis-urea de-

rivative **6** between odd and even chains could effectively alter the complementary H-bonding directions and in turn could lead to different physical properties of the gel. The effect of this kind of orientation is compounded when the gelator molecule is coupled with a chiral substituent like (*S*)-1-phenylethyl group. As expected it was found that only molecules with even numbered spacers formed gels in CHCl_3 . The physical properties of the gels were probed with rheology. The response towards anions was supposedly along the expected lines as these ions compete for the hydrogen bonding sites of the gelator (Fig. 5).

While most typical observations associated with ion responsive gels include gels being weakened or completely broken in response to an externally added ion, Ogden *et al.* reported a rare instance of a macrocyclic gelator **7** which can gel water only in presence of certain anions¹¹. The efficiency of the anions to cause gelation was found to conform well to the Hofmeister series $\text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^-$.

Strongly hydrated anions (to the right) are known as

the salting-out or kosmotropic ions, and the less hydrated one as salting-in or chaotropic ions. It has been found in the course of investigation that the addition of kosmotropic ions resulted in a liquid phase, whereas the more chaotropic ions tend to induce gelation (Fig. 6).

Itagaki *et al.* reported a tris-urea based gelator (**8**) which showed multiple anion recognition in an acetone gel¹². The gel to sol phase transition in this case was initiated when I^- , Br^- , Cl^- , F^- ions were added to the gel.

Fig. 5. Gel of **6** CHCl_3 with $n = 2$ to 8 shows alternation from gel (even n) and sol (odd n). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 10. (© 2008 Royal Society of Chemistry).

Fig. 6. Images of products formed with 0.2 mol L⁻¹ solutions of 7, and salts. (a) LiCl, 1.26 mol L⁻¹, stable gel, (b) NaCl, 1.26 mol L⁻¹, incomplete gel, (c) La(NO₃)₃, 0.01 mol L⁻¹, stable translucent gel, and (d) NaI, 0.10 mol L⁻¹, transient gel (crystallisation has commenced in this image). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 11. (© 2008 Royal Society of Chemistry).

The gel broken by F⁻ showed markedly different behavior than the rest of the halides as it was found that the gel state can be restored by adding BF₃·Et₂O to it. More remarkably it was found that ZnBr₂ can act as a non specific chemical stimulus and can regulate the gelation of all the solutions containing I⁻, Br⁻, Cl⁻, F⁻ ions (Fig. 7).

The changes induced by the anions are not exclusive only to the mechanical properties of the gel but can also induce changes in the optical and physical properties as demonstrated by Lee *et al.* This group reported a benzoxazole based derivative (9) that showed remarkable increase in fluorescence when it formed a gel in DMF/toluene mixture¹³. The gel also showed the ability to detect F⁻ ions exclusively by undergoing a gel to sol transition accompanied by a visible color change. The sensitivity towards the F⁻ ions was found to be quite high as it could be detected at very low concentrations. Though the disruption of gel structure also occurred with other anions the change of color took place only with F⁻ (Fig. 8).

The role played by anions could also be so specific such that self aggregation or gelation would occur only in the presence of a particular anion. Steed and co-workers designed one such anion tunable, shear induced metallo-gel¹⁴ where a gel resulted by a mere shaking of the mixture of a metal ion and a ligand containing solutions. The constituents of the gels are reported to be the methanolic solutions (1% w/v) of Cu(Br)₂ and a bis(urea) based ligand 10 in 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 equivalent ratios with respect to the metal ion. These gels were found to be robust and homogeneous in nature where as all other ratios of cation to ligand resulted in either weak gels or a precipitate. The role of the bromide as anion was very important for gel formation because anions such as Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, OAc⁻ and BF₄⁻ did not support shear induced gelation. The unique role of bromide as anion was proved by the addition of one equivalent of tetrabutylammonium (TBA) acetate and breakage of the gel by shaking within half an hour of addition. The gel reformed again when 1 equivalent of Cu(BF₄)₂ was added (Fig. 9).

The role of anions in gelation gains further importance if the resultant self assembled system has a biological application. Das and co-workers have tried success-

fully to inhibit the growth of various types of microbes, bacterial strains and fungal strains using a amphiphilic hydrogelator **11** whose efficiency changes with the counter anion¹⁵. When the counter anion was *n*-hexanoate, the

gel system showed five-fold higher antibacterial activity against Gram-positive *B. subtilis* along with enhanced biocompatibility than its chloride analogue. It was convenient to synthesize silver nanoparticles *in situ* in the supramolecular gel network when the counter anions were carboxylates. The resultant lyophilized composite nanomaterial was not only efficient against Gram-positive bacteria but also against Gram-negative bacteria such as *E. coli* and *K. aerogenes*.

Redox responsive systems

After the discussion of stimuli such as acids, cations

Fig. 7. Gel to sol transition of (a) gelator **8**, (b) with addition tetrabutylammonium halide with different anions and restoration of gel nature, (c) and (d) with the addition of non specific chemical stimuli. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 12. (© 2007 Elsevier).

Fig. 8. Photographs of **9** (A) in DMF-toluene mixture (9.52 × 10⁻⁵ M, 1 : 58 (v/v)); and (B) gel upon addition of 100 equiv. of anion. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 13. (© 2008 Royal Society of Chemistry).

and anions it will be interesting to know how electron transfer to a self assembled system affects its photophysical properties. Wang *et al.* reported a self assembled system which is responsive to reduction. In fact, this was the first example of an electron-induced Near InfraRed (NIR) supramolecular chiroptical switch that worked as a result of the changes in the electronic states of the chromophores rather than the structure of the chiral assembly¹⁶. A naphthalene diimide derivative **12** bearing two sugar groups formed organogels and exhibited absorption (Fig. 10) and Circular Dichroism (CD) as a result of the stacking of naphthalene chromophoric backbone and the induction of chirality from sugar moieties. Stacking of π surfaces in the backbone led to the formation of helical supramolecular self assembly with chiral electrochromic dyes. This chiral self assembly exhibited reversible and drastic changes in absorption and CD values especially in the NIR region (1310–1550 nm) when the dye was electrochemically reduced to its radical anion and the dianion.

Fig. 9. Cu^{2+} induced reformation of a gel of **10** with CuBr_2 (0.3 equiv.) in MeOH (from left to right) before shaking, after shaking, 5 min after injection of TBA acetate (1 equiv.), 30 min after injection of TBA acetate, and 5 min after injection of $\text{Cu}(\text{BF}_4)_2$ (1 equiv.). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 14. (© 2010 Royal Society of Chemistry).

Fig. 10. UV-Visible-NIR absorption of films of gel of **12** in butanol. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 16. (© 2008 American Chemical Society).

The ability to exhibit Cotton effect over the wide range of the spectrum (UV-Visible-NIR region) in different forms (neutral, anionic, dianionic) makes this molecule a very good chiroptical switch.

Solvent dependent systems

The solvent also plays an important role in aggregation and the mode of it. Ajayaghosh and co-workers reported a solvent-directed self assembly based on an amino acid linked π -conjugated system¹⁷. Enantiomeric **13** and **14** which are based on oligo(*p*-phenylenevinylene) backbone formed gels in chloroform and toluene. Both the derivatives have different morphological features in chloroform and toluene. SEM images obtained from the xerogels of **13** and **14** from chloroform revealed macroporous honeycomb architectures [Fig. 11(a) and

11(b)] aligned in a hexagonal fashion where as SEM images acquired from xerogels of toluene exposed the fibrous network [Fig. 11(c) and 11(d)]. This suggested different modes of aggregation in different solvents. In this system it seems like 1D aggregation leads to the formation of hexagonal honey comb structures where as 2D cross linkage leads to well aligned fibrous network.

Metal coordination

Metal coordination has also been investigated extensively for the gel formation. Gels promoted by such type of interactions are typically called metallo gels. These materials have gained a lot of importance in a number of applications such as synthesis, catalysis and stimuli sensitivity because of the presence of metal centers. Herein we discuss some representative examples of responsive metallo gels with potential to be applied as catalysts, nature mimics to build nanostructures etc.

Metallo gels as catalysts

Pd^{II} complexes have been extensively used as catalysts in a number of coupling reactions. Zhang and co-workers reported a palladium based metallo gel which catalyzed Suzuki and Suzuki-Miyaura coupling reactions (Scheme 1) almost in quantitative yields especially when the metal to ligand (**1**) ratio is 1 : 1¹⁸. Ligand **15** has all three important factors needed for self-assembly such as (a) amide functionality which helps in extensive hydrogen bonding (as donor and acceptor both), (b) aromatic moieties leading to π - π stacking and more importantly, (c) chelating ability. Pd^{II} ions formed gels with **15** in methanol-chloroform mixture (1 : 1 v/v) with different metal to ligand ratios (1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4, 3 : 4)]. In presence of 1 mmol % of this gel as catalyst in the coupling reaction between bromoacetophenone and

Fig. 11. SEM of xerogels of (a) 13 from toluene, (b) 14 from toluene, (c) 13 from chloroform, (d) 14 from chloroform. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 17. (© 2009 Wiley VCH).

Scheme 1. (a) Suzuki-Miyaura coupling and (b) Suzuki coupling; both in the presence of 1 mmol % of the Pd : 15 (1 : 1) gel.

phenylboronic acid the product was obtained in more than 99% yield which is a significant improvement from conventional catalysts.

Metallogels as templates for nanostructures

Besides catalysis, these types of gels have also been used for various other applications like being used as templates for designing complex nanostructures such as particles, tubes, helices etc. Helical structures are ubiquitous in *Nature* which form central structural building blocks in biological systems from nano versions of DNA double helix and collagen triple helix to microscopic viruses and macroscopic sea shells^{19a,b}. Nature has designed many complex dynamic systems to synthesize these helical structures with all kinds of desired shapes and sizes. It therefore remains a big challenge for us to understand and

mimic them to generate complex nanostructures synthetically. Past few years have seen a surge in the interest towards this particular field of research. Along these lines, Huang *et al.* recently reported metal driven hierarchical supramolecular self assemblies with sodium cholate^{19b}. Nano helices were observed in SEM, TEM and AFM studies of calcium(II) cholate gel (Fig. 12) and cholate gels of Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺. These nano helices were used to prepare inorganic chiral structures by two different methods. In the first method nano helices of silica (SiO₂) were obtained by the sol-gel method^{19c}. Huang's group was able to observe nano helical assemblies of silica in calcium-cholate (1 : 1) gel (Fig. 13). They also noticed semiconducting ZnS helical nanotubes when Na₂S was added to the Zn-cholate self assembly. This simple technique of self-templating was also used to prepare nanotubes of CuS, NiS, CdS, CoS, CdSe, CdTe

Fig. 12. Morphology of calcium-cholate supramolecular nano-helices (a) TEM image of right-handed nano-helices; (b) Tapping-mode AFM height image revealing helical features; (c) high-magnification of the boxed area in (b); (d) corresponding cross-sectional analysis of nanohelices showing uniform pitches. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 19b. (© 2009 American Chemical Society).

Fig. 13. (a) SEM and (b,c) TEM images of helical SiO₂ by sol-gel transcription. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 19b. (© 2009 American Chemical Society).

with control over the size on the nano structures just by controlling temporal and thermal conditions²⁰.

Lanthanide based metallogels

After the discussion about the 'P' and 'D' block metal ion based gels and materials it will be relevant to mention about gels based on even heavier metal ions such as lanthanides. One of the most interesting features of these ions is their photoluminescence. Due to photoluminescence property of lanthanide ions they have generated enormous interest to be used in wide variety of applications like in chemical or biological sensors, medical diagnostics, cell imaging, and thin film devices²¹.

Taking a lead from the synthesis of chiral silica structures, Huang and co-workers further synthesized silica nanotubes with doping of lanthanide ions to generate photoluminescent nanomaterials. In this context, synthesis of silica nanoparticles embedded with lanthanides has already been reported by Bunzli²². Silica which acts as stabilizer and protector of functional entities allows its optical activity to be measured due its chemical inertness and optical transparency. Huang was able to obtain photoluminescent nano silica initially by preparing silica via sol-gel method in the lanthanide-cholate self assembly followed by self-incorporation of lanthanide ions into silica nanotubes walls. The diameter of the silica nanotubes can be controlled by adjusting the temperature during the process. Silica nanotubes with Eu^{3+} , Tb^{3+} and $\text{Eu}^{3+}/\text{Tb}^{3+}$ mixtures which generated various photoluminescent colors were obtained (Fig. 14)²³.

dehyde, benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane, and *meta*-nitrobenzoylacetone. Numerous examples have since been published which successfully demonstrated lanthanide sensitization by complexation methods²⁴.

Recently, our group has come up with a strategy where trivalent lanthanides were shown to induce gelation of water in presence of stoichiometric sodium cholate. More remarkably, the lanthanide ion was shown to be sensitized by a suitable dopant *without the involvement* of any covalent linkage²⁵. Naturally, the advantage of this self assembly approach lies in the fact that it does not require any laborious synthetic procedure. Pyrene was shown to sensitize Eu^{3+} at very low levels of doping (as low as 2 μM). A solution of europium acetate (10 mM) was found to gel upon mixing with 30 mM aqueous solution of sodium cholate. When time delayed fluorescence spectra were recorded by exciting the gel at 335 nm, the results clearly demonstrated that the luminescence intensity of Eu^{3+} was

Fig. 14. (a-c) Silica nanotubes obtained from Tb^{3+} -cholate (3.0 mM/1.5 mM) hydrogel, (b-d) silica nanotubes obtained from $\text{Tb}^{3+}/\text{Eu}^{3+}$ -cholate, (a) and (d) are FESEM images, (b) and (e) are TEM images, (c) and (f) are room temperature emission spectra of silica nanotubes. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 (© 2011 American Chemical Society)

Sensitization of lanthanides in metallo gels

Lanthanides have unique photoluminescence properties as a result of f-f transitions. The consequences being long lifetimes, sharp line like emissions that are almost independent of external environment. Because of the forbidden nature of the f-f transition, they suffer from with very low ϵ values (about $10 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). But this problem has been overcome by using antenna groups for sensitization. Wisemann was the first to discover this phenomenon when Eu^{3+} ions were complexed with salicylal-

dehyde enhanced 10 fold in the presence of about 6 μM pyrene compared to the Eu -cholate gel without pyrene (Fig. 15).

After the successful discovery of self assembly (gel) based sensitization of Eu^{3+} in a non-coordinative fashion with pyrene we found that 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (DHN) could exclusively sensitize and in turn enhance the luminescence of Tb^{3+} in the gel state. Luminescence was enhanced by around 7.5 times [Fig. 16(a)] by doping of 10 μM DHN to Tb^{3+} -cholate hydrogel (5 mM/15 mM) resulting in a bright green luminescent gel²⁶ [Fig. 16(b)].

Fig. 15. (a) Time delayed emission spectra of Eu^{3+} -cholate (5 mM/15 mM) in the presence of pyrene when excited at 335 nm; (b) Eu^{3+} -cholate (5 mM/15 mM) gel under normal light; (c) under UV (365 nm) in the presence of pyrene (6 μM). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 25. (© 2010 Royal Society of Chemistry).

Fig. 16. (a) Time delayed emission spectra of Tb^{III} cholate (5/15 mM) gel without and with different concentrations of DHN and (b) photograph of a Tb^{III} cholate (5/15 mM) gel doped with 400 μM DHN under UV light of 365 nm. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 26. (© 2011 Royal Society of Chemistry).

Several reports exist in the literature showing efficient energy transfer between Tb^{3+} - Eu^{3+} . Brittain reported Tb^{3+} to Eu^{3+} energy transfer in the mixed complexes of dipicolinic acids in aqueous media^{27a}. Other reports include Tb^{3+} - Eu^{3+} energy transfer in polymers^{27b,c}, complex media^{27d}, zeolite cavities^{27e} etc. this particular phenomenon has also enabled researchers to generate tunable light emitting materials. When we tried to extend this idea to our cholate gel systems, energy transfer from Tb^{3+} - Eu^{3+} was indeed observed. The resultant luminescence depended on the ratio of concentrations of red emitting Eu^{3+} and green emitting Tb^{3+} . A reddish-pink luminescent gel was obtained when $\text{Tb}^{3+}/$

Eu^{3+} ratio was 4 mM/1 mM in 15 mM cholate and an yellow luminescent gel was obtained when $\text{Tb}^{3+}/\text{Eu}^{3+}$ ratio was 4.9 mM/0.1 mM in 15 mM cholate [Fig. 17(a) and 17(b)].

Xerogels of pyrene-doped Eu^{3+} -cholate and DHN-doped Tb^{3+} -cholate [Fig. 17(c) and 17(d)] were obtained doped with their respective sensitizers by freeze drying. Solid state time delayed spectra showed enhancement in the sensitization of lanthanide ions which was comparable with that of the gel state. However the efficiency of energy transfer from Tb^{3+} - Eu^{3+} decreased to some extent in the solid state.

Fig. 17. All photographs under UV (365 nm) (a) Gel of $Tb^{3+}/Eu^{3+}/NaC$ (4.9 mM/0.1 mM/15 mM); (b) Gel of $Tb^{3+}/Eu^{3+}/NaC$ (4 mM/1 mM/15 mM); (c) Xerogel of 12 μM pyrene doped Eu^{3+} -cholate (5 mM/15 mM); (d) Xerogel of 400 μM DHN doped Tb^{3+} -cholate (5 mM/15 mM). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 26. (© 2011 Royal Society of Chemistry).

Conclusion

In this mini review we have discussed various types of supramolecular gels responsive to a range of stimuli and each offering a unique property and advantage of being used as potential smart materials. Hybrid materials were discussed in which metal nanoparticles are stabilized/immobilized/synthesized in the gel matrix by incorporating appropriate functionalities in the gel structure. These are novel composites with interesting properties and sometimes even exhibit biological activities increasing their potential remarkably. Templated synthesis of inorganic nanostructures using the gel matrix in a selective and controlled fashion has also been highlighted. The gel matrix was also utilized to sensitize lanthanides by doping a chromophore in a non-coordinative fashion. Energy transfer between lanthanides was exploited to generate various colored luminescent gels and processable xerogels with promising optoelectronic applications.

The various types of supramolecular assemblies thus can provide a diverse array of materials with distinct physical properties for a wide range of applications in biomedicine, tissue engineering, synthesis hybrid materials etc. Moreover the possibility of designing and fine tuning suitable assembling building blocks that can be regulated by external stimuli has been the most promising aspect of supramolecular assemblies. There has been a surge in recent years in the discovery of such systems as it is evident now that such systems hold particular promise in design and synthesis of advanced materials for future applications.

References

- (a) N. M. Sangeetha and U. Maitra, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2005, **34**, 821; (b) J. W. Steed, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 1379; (c) A. Dawn, T. Shiraki, S. Haraguchi, S. Tamaru and S. Shinkai, *Chem. Asian J.*, 2011, **6**, 266.
- (a) A. R. Hirst, B. Escuder, J. F. Miravet and D. K. Smith, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 8002; (b) M. Zelzer and R. V. Ulijn, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 3351.
- P. Terech and R. G. Weiss, *Chem. Rev.*, 1997, **97**, 3133.
- S. Banerjee, R. K. Das and U. Maitra, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2009, **19**, 6649.
- J. W. Chung, B. K. An and S. Y. Park, *Chem. Mater.*, 2008, **20**, 6150.
- J. H. Jung, H. Kobayashi, M. Masuda, T. Shimizu and S. Shinkai, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 8785.
- S. Dong, Y. Luo, X. Yan, B. Zheng, X. Ding, Y. Yu, Z. Ma, Q. Zhao and H. Huang, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 1905.
- C. M. Micklitsch, P. J. Knerr, M. C. Branco, R. Nagarkar, D. J. Pochan and J. P. Schneider, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **7**, 1577.
- Q. Liu, Y. Wang, W. Li and L. Wu, *Langmuir*, 2007, **23**, 8217.
- M. O. M. Piepenbrock, G. O. Lloyd, N. Clarke and J. W. Steed, *Chem. Commun.*, 2008, 2644.
- T. Becker, C. Y. Goh, F. Jones, M. J. McIlldowie, M. Mocerino and M. I. Ogden, *Chem. Commun.*, 2008, 3900.
- M. Yamanaka, T. Nakamura, T. Nakagawa and H. Itagaki, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 8990.
- T. H. Kim, M. S. Choi, B. H. Sohn, S. Y. Park, W. S. Lyood and T. S. Lee, *Chem. Commun.*, 2008, 2364.
- M. O. M. Piepenbrock, N. Clarke and J. W. Steed, *Soft. Matter.*, 2010, **6**, 3541.
- S. Dutta, A. Shome, T. Kar and P. K. Das, *Langmuir*, 2011, **27**, 5000.
- J. Zheng, W. Qiao, X. Wan, J. P. Gao and Z. Y. Wang, *Chem. Mater.*, 2008, **20**, 6163.
- S. S. Babu, S. Mahesh, K. K. Kartha and A. Ajayaghosh, *Chem. Asian J.*, 2009, **4**, 824.
- Y. R. Liu, L. He, J. Zhang, X. Wang and C. Y. Su, *Chem. Mater.*, 2006, **18**, 4224.

19. (a) J. P. R. O. Orgel, T. C. Irving, A. Miller and T. J. Wess, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 2006, **103**, 9001; (b) Y. Qiao, Y. Lin, Y. Wang, Z. Yang, J. Liu, J. Zhou, Y. Yan and J. B. Huang, *Nano. Lett.*, 2009, **9**, 12; (c) Though, this process was not new and was first introduced by Shinkai to prepare silica nanotubes from an acetic acid-water gelator and later adopted by many others.
20. (a) Y. Qiao, Y. Wang, Z. Yang, Y. Lin and J. B. Huang, *Chem. Mater.*, 2011, **23**, 1182; (b) Y. Qiao, Y. Lin, Z. Yang, H. Chen, S. Zhang, Y. Yan and J. B. Huang, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 11725.
21. (a) K. Binnemans, *Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **109**, 4283; (b) M. Bottrill, L. Kwok and N. J. Long, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2006, **35**, 557; (c) C. M. G. Dos Santos, A. J. Harte, S. J. Quinn and T. Gunnlaugsson, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **252**, 2512; (d) J. H. Yu, D. Parker, R. Pal, R. A. Poole and M. J. Cann, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 2294; (e) G. S. Shao, R. C. Han, Y. Ma, M. X. Tang, F. X. Xue, Y. L. Sha and Y. Wang, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2010, **16**, 8647; (f) C. H. Song, Z. Q. Ye, G. L. Wang, J. L. Yuan and Y. F. Guan, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2010, **16**, 6464; (g) E. Deiters, B. Song, A. S. Chauvin, C. D. B. Vandevyver, F. Gumy and J.-C. G. Bünzli, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2009, **15**, 885.
22. S. V. Eliseeva, B. Song, C. D. B. Vandevyver, A.-S. Chauvin, J. B. Wacker and J.-C. G. Bünzli, *New J. Chem.*, 2010, **34**, 2915.
23. Y. Qiao, H. Chen, Y. Lin, Z. Yang, X. Cheng and J. B. Huang, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2011, **15**, 7323.
24. (a) K. Hanaoka, K. Kikuchi, H. Kojima, Y. Urano and T. Nagano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 12470; (b) K. Hanaoka, K. Kikuchi, H. Kojima, Y. Urano and T. Nagano, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2003, **42**, 2996; (c) S. Mizukami, K. Tonai, M. Kaneko and K. Kikuchi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **130**, 14376; (d) J. R. Perez, F. Nome and J. H. Fendler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 7749; (e) G. D. Correll, R. N. Cheser, F. Nome and J. H. Fendler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 1254; (f) C. S. Bonnet, L. Pellegatti, F. Buron, C. M. Shade, S. Villette, V. Kubíček, G. Guillaumet, F. Suzenet, S. Petoud and E. Toth, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 124.
25. S. Bhowmik, S. Banerjee and U. Maitra, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **45**, 8642.
26. S. Banerjee, K. Ramesh, S. Bhowmik and U. Maitra, *Soft. Matter.*, 2011, **7**, 8207.
27. (a) H. G. Brittain, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 2762; (b) S. V. Eliseeva, D. N. Pleshkov, K. A. Lyssenko, L. S. Lepnev, J.-C. G. Bünzli and N. P. Kuzmina, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 9300; (c) N. Kerbellec, D. Kustaryono, V. Haquin, M. Etienne, C. Daiguebonne and O. Guillou, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2009, **48**, 2837; (d) J. M. de Souza, S. Alves, G. F. De Sa and W. M. de Azevedo, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2002, **344**, 320; (e) Y. Tsukahara, M. Sato, S. Katagiri, T. Honda, K. Nakamura and Y. Wada, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2008, **451**, 194.

